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Demand for Primary Health Care Services: Evidence from Rural Bangladesh

Md. Bakhtiar Uddin*

***Abstract:** This study attempts to find the factors which significantly determine the demand for primary health care services in rural Bangladesh. For this study, Community Clinic (CC) in rural Bangladesh has been chosen as a case of primary health care service provider. By applying an econometric model with the data of 173 households from Mymensingh district of Bangladesh, we find that commuting time to health facilities; quality of services; availability of drug store or quack (paraprofessional) near to households; education of service taker and; number of female family member aged 18 years or above are highly statistically significant determinants of demand for primary health care services. Other factors such as wealth, income, age and gender, however, are found statistically insignificant. This study put forward to increase quality of the services as well as providing normal child delivery facility at the Community Clinic.*

***Keywords:** Community clinic, health care demand, determinants, primary health care, Bangladesh.*

Introduction

Across the world, there prevails inequality in accession to health services. In low- and middle-income countries, this phenomenon is quite visible (Peters, 2008). To reduce the health-gap between rich and poor much more emphasis is put on alternative service delivery, focusing the poor (ibid). Accordingly, Bangladesh government has underscored proving primary health services in rural area. In this regards, successive governments have taken innovative approaches such as community-based approach; community health workers; partnership with government and non-government organizations (NGOs) (Arifeen et al., 2013). These approaches distinguish Bangladesh from others. To provide health services to the poor at grass root level, a new layer of health care service delivery, named Community Clinic, to the existing national delivery system has been introduced under public sector in the rural community. CC is a small clinic at the grass root level, including the remotest and hard to reach area. The clinic is aimed to bring primary health care services at the doorstep of the rural people all over Bangladesh.

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There may be a specific pattern in demanding CC health care services. Various socio-economic factors such as age, gender, distance to CC, income, assets and so on may play an important role in demanding CC services. With these settings, the study will attempt to identify the determinants of demand for CC services.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the specific objectives of the research. Section 3 underscores the rationale of the study. Section 4 describes the data collection procedure and the quantitative technique to investigate the determining factors of primary health care demand. Section 5 presents short literature review on the determinants of primary health care demand. Section 6 and 7 present the socio-economic background of the respondents and the study findings. Finally, section 8 concludes with the key policy recommendations.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objective of the study is to identify the determinants of the demand for CC health care services. In addition, light will be shed on other aspects of the CC such as pattern of service delivery and patients' preferences.

The Rationale of the Study

To best of our knowledge, there has been no quantitative study, exploring the objectives of the current study. As the government has attached top most priority to the CC project, and as it is related to grass root poor people, it is highly pertinent to determine the factors playing role in accessing the services provided by CC. Determinants of demand for CC health care may be different than those found in other studies since CC provides services to the poor people at their doorsteps as well as the fees for the service is minimal. Lack of knowledge about the CC services and presence of rural quack (paraprofessional) at the close proximity of the service seeker may be important determinants of the demand for services. Other bottlenecks of the service delivery may be determining factors. Therefore, identification of significant conditions that ease access to the services as well as the factors that hinder people from accessing the service will put forward suggestions to the policymakers in devising appropriate policies.

Methodology

The study consulted available literature in relation to CC and community-based health care services in Bangladesh and other countries. In this regards, secondary sources such as journal articles, newspaper articles, periodicals, reports, books, websites of relevant offices have been surveyed. Purposively, the primary data have been collected from six villages under the *Trishalupazila* (sub-district) of *Mymensingh* district in Bangladesh. The sample villages surveyed are more or less similar to other rural areas. Because of budget constraint, the survey has not been extended to other parts of Bangladesh. A total of 173 households have been surveyed from the chosen villages with well-structured questionnaires. The households were chosen randomly from the catchment area under each CC. In the

case of minor children or absent sick person, father/ mother/senior family member has been asked the study questions. To reduce bias and to maintain the accuracy of data, the questionnaire has been pre-tested. Seven graduate and undergraduate students of University have been employed to collect data. Before collecting data, the enumerators were trained on data collection although they have adequate knowledge about research methodology and statistics as they have completed courses on research methods and statistics. In addition to the quantitative method, qualitative methods such as in-depth informal interview, key informant interview, and Focus Group Discussion (FDG) with the health care providers and the service seekers have been used to gather qualitative data. Lastly, collected data have been analyzed using statistical software called STATA. We have employed an econometric model to identify the determinants of health care demand for CC. Other findings of the study have been presented by employing descriptive statistics technique.

Literature Review on Determinants of Health Care

There is a growing body of literature investigating determinants of health care services in different countries and different service delivery channels. On the one hand, Akin et al. (1981) Heller (1982), Akin et al. (1986), Schwartz et al. (1988), and Ching (1995) find that fees for medical services do not significantly determine the demand for health care services. On the other hand, Mwabu (1986) and Gertler et al. (1987) find that fees are the major determinants of health care services. There may be differences in the health care system and health care management in the countries where those studies are conducted, which might have been significant for the opposing results. Studies in different countries pointed to other determinants such as availability of health care services (Akbari et al. 2009), location and socioeconomic characteristics (Appiah-Kubi 2004), waiting time (Ichoku and Lcibbrandt 2003), and distance to health care provider (Dor et al. 1987 and Mwabu et al. 1993)

Dor and Gaag (1988) study the health care determinant in developing countries. They pay special focus on rural Cote d'Ivoire. Their findings show that average time travelled to reach local health facilities, income, and age play a significant role in demanding primary health care. The adult person also significantly demand more health care compared to other age groups.

A study by Sahn et al. (2002) in rural Tanzania conveys two important messages. Firstly, quality is an important determinant of health demand. This applies to the quality and availability of doctors/nurses, drugs, and the clinic environment. The demand for health care will increase if people have the option to see a better doctor/nurse, get access to pharmaceuticals, and attend a health centre/clinic/ dispensary that is cleaner having toilet and water facilities. Secondly, consumers in Tanzania are highly responsive to the price of health care, and that this responsiveness is greater for individuals at the lower end of the income distribution.

Hotchkiss (1993) empirically studies the demand for medical care which includes information on the provider's attributes as well as individual characteristics. Empirical results suggest that facility attributes that influence the quality of care, such as crowding, practitioner training, and drug availability are significant determinants of the choice of the obstetric care provider. Results also indicate that the interaction between price and household wealth has an important effect on choice. In particular, the findings suggest that price is a statistically significant determinant of the demand for healthcare for poor households, but not for others.

Ali and Noman (2013) investigate determinants of health care demand in Bangladesh and find that level of education, income, quality of care; fees for medical services and price of drugs play a significant role in demanding health care.

Aldana et al.(2001) investigate client satisfaction and quality of health care in rural Bangladesh. They find providers' behaviour, especially respect and politeness, as the most powerful predictor for client satisfaction with the government services. For patients, this aspect is found much more important than the technical competence of the providers have. Furthermore, the waiting time is a major determinant.

A study of Ahmed et al. (2005) in Bangladesh on socio-economic conditions and the differences in health-seeking behaviour between younger (aged 20 to 59) and elderly (aged above 60) does not find any statistically significant differences in health-seeking behaviour between these two groups.

The Study Population

A total of 173 households from 6 localities within the catchment area of six different CCs such as *Chikna*, *BoilorPuraton Bazar*, *BaganModdhopara*, *Konabari*, *Mothbari* and *Sakhua* under *Trishal* upazilla have been surveyed. Table 6.1 presents the distribution of households.

Table 1: Distribution of households

Name of area	No. of observations	Percent
<i>Chikna</i>	39	22.54
<i>BoilorPuraton Bazar</i>	46	26.59
<i>BaganModdhopara</i>	18	10.40
<i>Konabari</i>	22	12.72
<i>Mothbari</i>	19	10.98
<i>Sakhua</i>	29	16.76
Total	173	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2018

The study covers sick individuals aged a minimum of 0.3 to a maximum of 95 years. The average age of the sick people surveyed is 34.58 year. Most of the sick people (59%) of the sample are female. Out of 173 sick people, 132 (76%) are married, while 41 (24%) are unmarried.

On average, each household has 6 six members. The lowest number of household member is 1, while the highest is 22. The number of members is categorized in three age-categories such as 0 to below 3 years, 3 to 5 five years and female with the age of 18 years or above.

Most of the sick person surveyed (64) have no formal education. A total of 58 persons attained a secondary and higher secondary degree, while 23 attained class eight. Only 5 persons are reported attaining up to class four. Average years of schooling of the household heads are reported 5.67 years, ranging from 0 to 17 years. Average years of schooling of mothers in the households are reported 3.67 years, ranging from 0 to 17 years.

On average, each household earns BDT 23,323 in per month. Significant variation in monthly income among the households is reported with a standard deviation of BDT 27,543. Minimum monthly income is BDT 500, while the maximum is BDT 200,000. The average wealth of each household is BDT 2,941,810 with a standard deviation of BDT 4,154,585. This huge standard deviation reflects wider inequality of wealth among the surveyed households.

Major Findings

To have information regarding determinants of demand for primary health care services we asked people whether they were sick last six months. They responded that they suffered from a range of illnesses such as fever, pain, physical weakness, cold/cough, skin disease, diarrhea, headache, nausea/vomit, in appetence, insomnia, a problem in the ear, cataract/ night-blindness, pregnancy-related problem, disease related to female. Many others visited health facilities for some other diseases such as prolonged illness, cardiovascular problem, fracture, mental problem, and so on. About 17 percent of the respondents replied that they visited health facilities for a fever. About 12 and 10 percent of the respondents visited for cold/cough and pain, respectively. For skin disease and diarrhea, about 9 percent of the respondents went to health facilities.

It is found during the survey that people firstly visit nearby health facilities, drug store, quack for the primary measure of treatment. Table 7.1 ranks primary actions for treatment among the sample of the study.

Table 2: Primary action of treatment

Rank	Action	No.of respondent	Percentage
1	CC	45	26.01
2	Upazilla health complex	32	18.50
3	Drug store	30	17.34
4	Quack	20	11.56
5	MBBS doctor	9	5.20
5	Private clinic	9	5.20
6	District general hospital	7	4.05
7	Religious rite based treatment	5	2.89

7	Traditional treatment by practitioner (<i>Kabiraz/Hekim</i>)	5	2.89
7	Traditional treatment at home	5	2.89
8	Homeopathy	4	2.31
9	No action	1	0.58
9	Paramedics	1	0.58
Total		173	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2018

The topmost destination for primary health care is CC followed by *upazilla* health complex, drug store and quack. Respondents also visited MBBS doctor around them (9%). They also visited the private clinic, usually far away from their residence. Some respondents also opted for religious rite based treatment, traditional treatment by the practitioner or traditional medicine at home.

The highest number of the respondents (27.27 %) visited *upazilla* health complex for the secondary measure of treatment. The second option was to visit district general hospital (25.27%). They also went to a private clinic and private MBBS practitioners. Very few respondents used traditional measures at this stage.

It is found that a significant number of respondents visited CC for both primary and secondary measures for treatment. On average, respondents visited CC 6 times during the last six months before the survey. Some respondent visited CC as high as 35 times. However, some respondents did not visit as they did not know about the CC services. Those who visited CC knew about the CC services through different sources such as health worker, friends, and family member, neighbour and television advertisement. Most of the respondents (about 54%) knew about CC through neighbour followed by health workers.

Distance to CC and condition of the way to CC can be an important determining factor of visiting CC. It is expected that if the distance to CC is longer than that of other health facilities, people will visit CC less although the direct cost of CC service is lower even may be zero because it will involve high opportunity cost in terms of time spent on commuting. People may lose direct income or indirect leisure due to travelling a long distance to CC. On the other hand, the unpaved or muddy road can prevent sick people from visiting CC. In that case, both direct transportation cost and indirect opportunity cost will be higher. The study found that, on average, distance to nearest CC was 1.57 kilometre, whereas it was 3.5 kilometre for nearest other health facilities. The way from most of the households to CC was unpaved soil (*kancha*) followed by pitched road and brick road. On average, it took 23 minutes to reach the nearest CC, while it took 43 minutes to reach other health facilities. Because of short distance and less time taken to reach CC, respondents opted for CC to avail primary health care compared to the union health centre or *upazilla* health complex.

Direct and indirect cost for primary health care services is a major determinant for the demand for particular health service. Even, in case of zero direct cost people may not demand a particular service if it involves large indirect cost or opportunity cost such as longer waiting time at the health facilities. This study investigated both the direct and indirect cost of illness. Generally, primary health care services are almost free at public health facilities in the rural area. Besides, there are some NGOs providing health care for free of charge in rural Bangladesh. Therefore, much attention is paid on the cost of commuting, diagnosis, medicine, or day lost due to illness. Focus is given on how much income forgone due to illness. About 42 percent of the respondents spent some amount in between BDT 0 and 1,000 and about 39 per cent spent between BDT 1000 and 5000. Only about 11 per cent spent between BDT 5,000 and 10,000. Some households found spending a higher amount. In that case, diseases were prolonged as well as much complicated that required special treatment. The average duration of last illness was 19 days and income-day lost due to illness in the last six months was 16 days. On average, respondents forgo BDT 4,592 because of not being able to work due to illness.

Respondents availed themselves with different types of health care's provided by the CC. The topmost reason for visiting CC was fever followed by family planning. Respondents also took treatment for cold/cough, diarrhea, pregnancy problem, infant health, physical weakness, skin disease, pain, and problem in relation to the ear, tuberculosis, malaria, headache, nausea/vomit, in appetite and insomnia. Some respondents visited CC for family planning education, nutritional supplements, and immunization as well.

Quality of health services depends on the skill of the doctor or health assistant and other facilities at the clinic such as the availability of pure drinking water, toilet, and waiting room. Quality also depends on the behaviour of the doctor/health assistant, other staffs. It is a common allegation against the doctor and clinic staff—be in a public or private clinic—is that they do not behave well with the patients or do not pay much attention to patients. Even, they do not want to know the problem of the patients in details by listening for a longer time. Moreover, the doctor's absenteeism is prevalent, especially in rural public health facilities. Waiting time for service maybe an important determinant of the quality of the service. Less the waiting time the less is the indirect costs. In this study, almost half of the respondents reported affirmatively about the availability of pure drinking water. Most of the respondents (about 66 %) reported that they used or saw toilet facility and 26.74 percent of them did not use that facility due to unavailability of the toilet at different clinics/health facilities. However, some respondents mentioned that although they found toilet facilities, their condition was very poor. About 67 percent of the respondents reported the presence of waiting room at clinics/health facilities and about 33 percent did not find any separate waiting room. Each respondent, on average, waited 10 minutes to receive health services. Waiting for only 10 minutes may not be very disgusting to the service seeker. The studies found that most of the respondents (67 %) were

satisfied with this waiting time. Overall, despite some hassles and mismanagement most of the respondents (62%) in the study sample were satisfied with the services provided by different service providers.

Table 2.2: Benefited or not from CC services

	Female	Male	Total
Benefited	69	43	112
Not benefited	33	28	61
Total	102	71	173

Source: Field survey, 2018

Table 7.2 shows the gender-wise level of benefit from CC. Out of 173 respondents, 61 respondents were not benefited from CC services because they did not visit CC. Among the not-visiting respondents, 28 were male and 33 were female. Rest 120 respondents were somehow benefited from CC services. Among the benefited group, female (69) are the main beneficiaries. Women might opt for CC more because of the proximity of the CC to the community. In the case of far-flung *upazila* health complex or district general hospital, women require their male counter parts to visit along with them. Unavailability of male counterpart during the hospital working hours discourages women to visit those distant health facilities. Closeness to the service provider at CC might have been another reason for women to visit CC more since the service provider might live in the same community from where the service seeker came.

Table 7.3: Summary statistics

Variable	No. of households	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
Primary action	173	7.335	2.745	0	12
Secondary action	143	8.927	2.902	0	12
No. of visit to CC	173	5.739	7.541	0	35
Weather know about CC	173	0.8786	0.327	0	1
How know about CC	157	2.471	0.859	1	5
Services availed from CC	119	9.478	5.431	1	23
Total medical cost	173	11115.4	78465.56	0	1000540
Distance to CC	173	1.575	2.362	0.1	20
Distance to other health center	170	3.508	2.192	1	18
Type of road to CC	172	1.633	0.891	1	3

Type of road to other health center	173	2.953	2.870	1	35
Commuting time to CC	173	22.520	22.262	2	180
Commuting time other health center	173	41.583	27.445	0	180
Waiting time	173	9.676	12.906	0	100
Whether satisfied with waiting time	167	0.670	0.471	0	1
Availability of free medicine	173	0.421	0.518	0	2
Presence of waiting room	173	0.953	1.346	0	17
Presence of toilet	172	0.802	0.547	0	2
Day lost due to illness	173	16	71.879	0	900
Income forgone due to illness	173	4592.48	11251.75	0	80000

Estimation

To determine major determinants of demand for CC we have set the following health care demand function.

$$M = M(A, B, C, D, E)$$

A= Vector of the indirect cost of illness

B= Vector of household characteristics

C= household income and assets

D= Quality of care

E= Home visit of health worker

We prefer to fit a to bit model because the dependent variable is both dummy and continuous. If the household member does not visit, then the variable takes the value of zero and if the member visits, then the variable takes the value of the number of visits. Descriptions of data and variables are given in the appendix.

Table 7.4: Summary statistics of explanatory variables

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Distance to CC (KM)	173	1.575	2.361	0.1	20
Time to reach CC (Min)	173	22.520	22.263	2	180
Quality of CC services	173	0.618	0.487	0	1

Years of schooling	173	5.664	5.139	0	17
Mother's years of schooling	172	3.669	4.456	0	17
Availability of drug store/quack	173	0.688	0.465	0	1
Age	173	34.578	19.299	.3	95
Gender	173	0.410	0.493	0	1
Married	173	0.763	.4264731	0	1
Household member below 3 years	173	0.474	0.678	0	3
Household member below 3-5 years	173	0.543	0.719	0	2
Female member above 18 years	173	0.722	0.718	0	3
Total monthly income	173	23323.12	27543.15	500	200000
Total assets	173	2941810	4154585	2500	2.91e+07
Duration of illness	173	19.017	28.331	0	200
Income lost due to illness	173	4592.486	11251.75	0	80000
Home visit of health worker	173	0.780	0.415	0	1

Table 7.4 presents summary statistics of the variable used in the econometric model. Table 7.5 reports to bit estimations of demand for CC health care. Column 1-6 presents marginal effects of various specifications of the model. Distance to CC from household is not statistically significant at conventional levels. It is statistically significant at 10 percent level only in one specification (column 3). Time to reach CC is highly statistically significant at 1 percent level in all specifications meaning that this factor is one of the major determinants for the demand for CC services. Increase in a one standard deviation of travelling time to CC reduces 4.5 times (22.263×0.203) visits to CC.

Table 7.5: To bit estimation of demand for CCservices

The dependent variable is number of visit to CC						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Variables	Marginal Effects					
Distance to CC (KM)	0.620 (0.473)	0.641 (0.484)	0.837* (0.495)	0.634 (0.484)	0.672 (0.486)	0.729 (0.489)
Time to reach CC (Min)	-0.203*** (0.0560)	-0.197*** (0.0564)	-0.200*** (0.0558)	-0.195*** (0.0571)	-0.203*** (0.0578)	-0.209*** (0.0582)
Quality of CC	8.127***	8.434***	7.983***	8.398***	8.269***	7.977***

services						
	(1.480)	(1.496)	(1.464)	(1.500)	(1.510)	(1.535)
Years of schooling	-0.254*	-0.254*	-0.180	-0.274*	-0.280*	-0.272*
	(0.151)	(0.150)	(0.150)	(0.162)	(0.163)	(0.163)
Mother's years of schooling	-0.463**	-0.584***	-0.571***	-0.583***	-0.618***	-0.640***
	(0.184)	(0.194)	(0.192)	(0.194)	(0.197)	(0.198)
Availability of drug store/quack	-3.623**	-3.492**	-3.479**	-3.518**	-3.689**	-3.992***
	(1.450)	(1.451)	(1.425)	(1.457)	(1.464)	(1.498)
Age		-0.0166	0.0265	-0.0200	-0.0188	-0.0185
		(0.0495)	(0.0509)	(0.0505)	(0.0516)	(0.0516)
Gender		1.034	0.619	0.982	1.162	1.324
		(1.526)	(1.489)	(1.539)	(1.578)	(1.585)
Married		-2.549	-3.651	-2.460	-2.195	-2.394
		(2.359)	(2.346)	(2.392)	(2.420)	(2.424)
Household member below 3			-1.235			
			(0.986)			
Household member 3-5 years			-0.161			
			(0.945)			
Female member above 18yrs			-2.764***			
			(1.055)			
Total monthly income				1.84e-06	4.20e-06	4.03e-06
				(2.50e-05)	(2.53e-05)	(2.53e-05)
Total assets				6.33e-08	7.80e-08	7.46e-08
				(1.81e-07)	(1.80e-07)	(1.81e-07)
Duration of illness					-0.00493	-0.000438
					(0.0258)	(0.0262)
Income lost due to illness					-7.76e-05	-7.99e-05
					(6.68e-05)	(6.70e-05)
Home visit of health worker						1.688
						(1.774)
Log likelihood	-444.66	-442.32	-438.18	-442.25	-441.40	-440.95
Observations	172	172	172	172	172	172

Note: Standard errors are in parenthesis, Asterisk ***, **, * indicates significance at 1, 5 and 10% level, respectively.

Quality of services is also highly statistically significant at 1 percent level in all specifications. This suggests that improvement in quality in terms of improvement in direct health care and other auxiliary facilities such as availability of waiting room, presence and usability of a toilet, availability of adequate free medicine and pure drinking water increase demand for CC health care. A one standard deviation improvement in quality increases demand for CC health care by almost 4 times (8.127×0.487). Level of education of the service taker is only significant at 10 percent level in all specifications. This variable is negatively associated with demand for CC health care. But in the case of minor children, level of education of the service taker may not influence demand because they do not take decision about which health facilities to choose. Ultimately, their parents decide on health facilities. To capture this parental decision, we have incorporated mother's level of education in the model. Mother's education is statistically significant at 1 percent level in all specifications. A one standard deviation increases in the year of schooling of mother decreases CC health care demand by 2 (4.456×0.463) meaning that sick people will visit CC by 2 times fewer. Availability of drug store or quack is also statistically highly significant at 1 percent level. The negative relation between drug store or quack has been detected. This means that member of households near to the drug store or quack visits CC by 3.623 times fewer compared to the member of households who does not have access to the drug store or quack. On the other hand, other personal and household characteristics are not statistically significant in any specifications at conventional levels of significance. These variables are age, gender, marital status, household member aged below 3years, household member aged 3-5years, household monthly income, household assets, duration of illness, income lost due to illness and home visit of health worker. However, household female member aged 18 years or above has been a statistically significant factor of CC health care demand. This has been the case because female under this age category mostly visits CC to avail themselves with primary reproductive health services.

Concluding Remarks

The study has investigated the determinants of CC health care demand as primary health care in Bangladesh. The study surveyed a sample of 173 households scattered in six different locations of *Trishalupazilla*, a sub-district of *Mymensingh*. The study investigates different socio-economic and personal characteristics of both the sick person and the households.

CC provides primary services including communicable disease, family planning and health education. The study found mixed responses among the respondents about the effectiveness of the service delivery. Some CCs have been found outperforming other CCs. Performance of the CCs depends on the quality of health assistance, their attitudes towards the service seeker and the local management.

Being located at the doorsteps of the service seekers, the CCs have opened a new avenue for the female service seeker. Women feel free to visit CC because of

location, a short distance from home, cultural similarity, and many other factors. In the study, it is found that women outnumbered their male counterpart in terms of frequency of visiting CCs. People from all walks of life, irrespective of wealth, education, and age, are found taking CC services.

Turning to the determinants of CC health care demand, a Tobit model is run to find statistically significant factors. Travelling time to CC, quality of services, availability of drug store or quack near to the service seekers appeared highly statistically significant determinants of demand for CC services. This study suggests enhancing the quality of services both direct medical care and some other indirect auxiliary services such as facilities of drinking water, waiting room, usable toilet and so on. Availability of free medicine also enhances the quality of the CC services. The education level of the service taker is found statistically significant factor as well. Minimum age of marriage for female in Bangladesh is 18 years. Thus, women aged 18 years or above can visit primary health care facilities for family planning and treatment for pregnancy. In this study, the member from households with more female members aged 18 years or above significantly demanded more CC services as compared to others. Wealth, income, age and gender, however, have been found statistically insignificant factors. This may be due to the nature of the care provided by the CC. Since CC provides only primary care, people with only primary disease visit CC. And as fees in CC are minimal, the price of the medical care does not play any role.

The study put forward suggestions to enhance the quality of CC services so that the maximum number of rural people can avail the benefits of the CC health care. In the focus group discussion, the respondents suggested increasing pregnancy and 'normal-delivery' cares for the women. In the rural area, in case of emergency, many of the delivery patients cannot reach *upazilla* or district hospitals in time because of long-distance and bad conditions of roads. Moreover, malpractice in private hospitals compels women to opt for unnecessary cesarean delivery across the globe (Niino, 2011), and Bangladesh is no exception. It is argued in medical research that cesarean delivery invites far-reaching negative impacts on the health of the mother and the baby (Card et al., 2018; Bager et al. 2008). Therefore, it is pertinent to increase normal-delivery services at the CC to stop malpractice at the private hospitals and thereby controlling their greediness for money at the same time avoiding long-term consequences on mother and baby's health. Moreover, this will ease the pressure on the *upazilla* and district hospitals; health workers there can devote more time and resources to more medically necessary cases.

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Appendix

Variable descriptions

CC health care demand: Number of times a household member visited CC in the last six months. We have taken long span of time, six months because CC health service is very new introduction to the health care system of Bangladesh. Many more people do not know about its services. The variable starts from zero--if not visited--then it takes continuous values depending on the number of visits.

Distance to community clinic: Distance to CC may influence the decision of taking primary health care services in terms of the opportunity cost of time and direct commuting costs involved. Long-distance of health centres may discourage health care service seeker because of psychic reason as well. People generally attach some sort of fear to a place far away from home. In this study, distance to CC is measured in kilometres.

Time to reach CC: Time taken to reach primary health facilities may affect the demand for health care. We have included this variable in addition to distance of CC because of the fact that due to bad condition of road or unavailability of means of communication travelling a short distance takes long time. In consequence, the service seekers may withhold their demand for service due to time costs. The variable is measured in minutes.

Quality of CC services: This variable is a dummy in nature--if satisfied with direct health services and other auxiliary facilities, it takes 1, and otherwise it takes 0. In this satisfaction decision, we have considered waiting time at CC, presence of waiting room, availability and usability of toilet; availability of pure drinking water, availability of adequate free medicine, presence of the health assistant and behaviour of the health assistant and other staffs.

Level of education: Level of education of the service taker and other members in the households can be crucial for demanding CC health services. We have surveyed the level of education of the service seeker, household head, mother or female household head and other family members. All these variables are measured in years of schooling.

Drug store/ Quack: In rural areas, a good number of seek people take primary health care from nearby drug store and paraprofessional village doctor or quack. Availability of them around the service seeker may prevent him/her from visiting CC. The variable is dummy in nature.

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Age: Age of the service seeker also may play a vital role in demanding CC services. It is expected that households with infant and elderly members will require more primary health care.

Gender: Demand for primary health services may be different for male and female. It is expected that female will frequently visit CC compared to their male counterpart because of family planning, family planning education and female related services provided by CC. The variable is a dummy in nature.

Marital status: Marital status can also play a vital role in demanding CC health care. Especially, married woman can visit CC frequently due to family planning, immunization, pregnancy-related services provided by CC. The variable is dummy variable.

Number of household member: Household members are classified into three categories such as children aged below 3 years, in between 3 and 5 years, an adult female of 18 years or above to investigate age-specific effects on CC health service demand.

Income: This variable is measured as the total monthly income in BDT.

Assets: Assets is measured as the present value of household wealth including cultivable land, homestead, house, agricultural and nonagricultural instruments, cattle, furniture, durable home appliances, vehicles etc.

Duration of illness: Duration of illness is measured in days.

Income lost due to illness: This variable also measures the indirect cost of illness in monetary terms.

Home visit of health worker: Dummy variable, whether health workers of different government organization and non-government organization visit home.